

Potential neuropsychiatric, analgesic and chemo-preventive properties of saffron

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Saffron (*Crocus sativus*) is a perennial herb that is primarily found in the Mediterranean region of Europe, western Asia, and the Kashmir region of India. The dried stigmas of the plant have been utilized as a spice, flavoring, and dyeing agent for over a millennium. The main constituents of saffron stigma responsible for major pharmacological effects are considered to be carotenoids (crocins, crocetins) and monoterpenes (picrocrocin, safranal). Potential pharmacological effects of saffron that have been investigated so far are anti-neuropathic pain effects, anticonvulsant and antidepressant effects, chemo-preventive, antibacterial, antifungal, antiseptic and anti-inflammatory properties. Research has suggested that saffron could potentially influence the activity of certain molecules, such as dopamine, TNF- α , Wnt/ β -catenin pathways, superoxide dismutase, catalase, and other antioxidant molecules [1]. Here author summarizes available up-to-date scientific evidence regarding the potential neuropsychiatric, analgesic and chemo-preventive properties of saffron.

Potential neuropsychiatric effects

According to a placebo-controlled randomized clinical trial (RCT), it was found that saffron capsules were not successful in decreasing food cravings. However, it may be a safe over-the-counter supplement that can assist in alleviating symptoms of mild to moderate depression in overweight individuals experiencing depression [2]. Results of a meta-analysis, in which RCTs conducted to year 2013 were included, indicate that saffron supplementation could improve symptoms of depression in adults with major depressive disorder [3]. Results of a study using mice showed potential anxiolytic and hypnotic effects of saffron aqueous extract and safranal [4]. Preclinical studies demonstrated that saffron exerts neuroprotective effects mostly via anti-oxidative stress, anti-neuro-inflammation and anti-apoptosis pathways [5]. The anticonvulsant activities of *Crocus sativus* stigma constituents, safranal and crocin, were evaluated in mice using pentylenetetrazole (PTZ)-induced convulsions in mice: safranal showed anticonvulsant activity, whilst crocin did not [6]. Several human and animal studies have provided some indication that saffron may possess anticonvulsant and anti-Alzheimer properties, potentially by increasing levels of glutamate and dopamine in the brain in a manner that depends on the dosage [7]. According to a meta-analysis from 2019, saffron may have a noteworthy impact on the severity of depression [8]. Studies in animals and humans have shown that saffron and its main component crocin may be effective against cognitive dysfunction and oxidative stress caused by chronic stress and may slow cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease. Some of the potential neuroprotective mechanisms of saffron include inhibiting the activity of acetylcholinesterase, reducing the formation of beta-amyloid plaques and tau protein tangles, exhibiting antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects, and promoting synaptic plasticity [9].

Based on the available scientific evidence saffron supplementation should be further investigated for its potentially beneficial neuropsychiatric effects, contributable mainly to its constituents safranal and crocin, via anti-oxidative stress, anti-neuro-inflammation and anti-apoptosis pathways. Studies showed that saffron could be superior to placebo and non-inferior to fluoxetine, citalopram and imipramine in the mitigation of depression symptoms severity. Saffron supplementation might be considered as generally safe nutritional

support and additional treatment for patients suffering from depression. In addition to that, some studies have shown that saffron might exert neuroprotective properties associated with inhibitory actions on acetylcholinesterase activity, reduced aggregation of beta-amyloid and tau proteins (prevention of amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles accumulation), all of which might be relevant for the prevention of Alzheimer's disease and the slowdown of cognitive decline.

Potential analgesic effects

An animal study showed that saffron and crocin (at dose 30 mg/kg) decreased thermal hyperalgesia and mechanical allodynia on day 26 after the nerve lesion caused by chronic constriction injury (CCI), and this effect continued until the day 40. These findings suggest that treatment with saffron and crocin (at a dose of 30 mg/kg) after the induction of a CCI may have a therapeutic effect against neuropathic pain [10]. The study aimed to examine the phytochemical properties and long-term effectiveness of *Crocus sativus* in treating neuropathic pain, and showed that the oxidative stress reduction, insulin secretagogue, and pancreatic beta-cells regeneration potentials might be responsible for the mechanism underlying the anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory and anti-neuropathic activities of saffron [11]. In a study conducted in 2017, researchers administered crocetin from saffron via intrathecal injection at various doses for up to 12 days, starting 3 days prior to surgery, in a mouse model for neuropathic pain induced by spared nerve injury (SNI). The results showed that repeated treatment with crocetin reduced mechanical and thermal sensitivity to pain, high doses of crocetin decreased the SNI-induced increase of TNF- α and IL-1 β , and crocetin restored the activity of the mitochondrial enzyme MnSOD (manganese superoxide dismutase) which was reduced in the sciatic nerve and spinal cord of the SNI mice [12]. Another study showed that treatment with crocetin from saffron via intrathecal injection significantly reduced mechanical allodynia and thermal hyperalgesia induced by CCI in 36 male Wistar rats ($P < 0.05$) and also significantly prevented the ineffective effects of atropine pre-treatment [13].

Here presented animal studies show that saffron constituents crocin and crocetin could have potential beneficial effects in the alleviation of neuropathic pain (reduction of thermal hyperalgesia and mechanical allodynia, anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic properties) in a synergistic and dose-dependent manner, wherefore saffron supplementation might also be relevant for the prevention/complementary symptomatic treatment of diabetic neuropathy, and should be considered for further investigation in this group of patients.

Potential chemotherapeutic properties

Saffron and its components, particularly crocin and crocetin, have been studied for their potential anti-tumor effects. The proposed mechanisms of action include inhibition of DNA and RNA synthesis, inhibition of free radical chain reactions, metabolic conversion to retinoids, interaction with an enzyme involved in DNA-protein interaction, and modulation of the immune system [14]. There is some evidence in the available scientific literature that saffron and its carotenoids crocin and crocetin could exert chemo-preventive activity

through antioxidant activity, induction of cancer cell apoptosis, inhibition of cell proliferation, enhancement of cell differentiation, modulation of cell cycle progression and cell growth, modulation of tumor metabolism, stimulation of cell-to-cell communication and immune modulation [15]. Results of a systematic review showed that saffron could have selective toxic and preventive effects on cancerous cells without adverse effects on normal cells when used in amounts that are not much higher than those used in human food culture [16].

Conclusion

There is some clinical evidence supporting the use of saffron supplementation for the alleviation of depression symptoms, especially in mild-to-moderate depression, which is probably attributable to its constituents safranal and crocin (anti-oxidative, anti-neuro-inflammation and anti-apoptosis effects). Saffron could also be considered as nutritional support for the prevention of Alzheimer's disease because of its potential neuroprotective properties (reduction of amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles). Animal studies showed the potential beneficial effects of saffron supplementation in the alleviation of neuropathic pain, and therefore it could be considered relevant in the prevention and/or complementary symptomatic treatment of diabetic neuropathy and further studied as such. Some evidence shows potential chemotherapeutic properties of saffron which could be toxic for cancer cells, but relatively non-toxic at the same dosage interval for normal cells. Therefore, further research on this subject might be interesting as well.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

RCT, randomized clinical trial; PTZ, pentylenetetrazole; CCI, chronic constriction injury; SNI, spared nerve injury; MnSOD, manganese superoxide dismutase.

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